

Identification of the gene immediately downstream of the murine INK4a/ARF locus

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Abstract

The tumor suppressor gene ARF is formed by three exons, namely exons 1 β , 2 and 3. Here, we show that embryo fibroblasts from mice genetically deficient in exons 2 and 3 (Δ 2,3) express a transcript formed by exon 1 β followed by the 3'-terminal exon of the gene immediately downstream of the INK4a/ARF locus, which we have called NTP16 (Next-To-p16). The chimeric ARF-NTP16 transcript is not detectable in wild-type fibroblasts but its expression level in Δ 2,3 fibroblasts is 30% compared to the level of the normal ARF transcript in wild-type cells. Expression of the ARF-NTP16 transcript in Δ 2,3 cells is subject to normal regulatory features, such as upregulation by the accumulation of cell doublings, and by the presence of oncogenic Ras or E1a. The chimeric ARF-NTP16 transcript has the potential to encode a 17 kDa peptide; however, this peptide is not accumulated in cells at detectable levels, probably reflecting poor codon usage or protein instability. We conclude that Δ 2,3 cells do not retain ARF functionality, at least to a significant extent. Interestingly, the expression pattern of the full-length NTP16 gene is altered in several tissues by the presence of the Δ 2,3 mutation. Finally, these data identify the gene immediately downstream of the INK4a/ARF locus, a region that has been previously proposed to contain another tumor suppressor different from the INK4a/ARF genes. © 2001 Elsevier Science Inc. All rights reserved.

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1. Introduction

The INK4a/ARF locus is regarded as one of the most important anti-tumoral defenses that mammalian organisms possess (Serrano, 1997; Weinberg, 1997; Ruas & Peters, 1998; Sherr, 1998; Sharpless & DePinho, 1999). Its two gene products, p16^{INK4a} and p19^{ARF}, regulate the activity of two other tumor suppressors, Rb and p53, respectively. The INK4a

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and ARF genes have their own separate promoters (Sherr, 1998; Sharpless & DePinho, 1999). The INK4a promoter generates a transcript formed by exons 1 α , 2 and 3, that encodes p16^{INK4a}, whereas the ARF promoter is located several kilobases upstream of exon 1 α , and generates a transcript formed by exons 1 β , 2 and 3, encoding p19^{ARF}. Although exons 2 and 3 are common to INK4a and ARF transcripts, they are read in different frames and, therefore, the corresponding proteins do not share amino acid sequence identity. Protein p16^{INK4a} binds and inhibits the Rb-kinases CDK4 and CDK6, thus resulting in cell-cycle arrest at early G1 (Serrano, 1997; Weinberg, 1997; Ruas & Peters, 1998). On the other hand, p19^{ARF} binds to the p53-destabilizing oncogene MDM2 and sequesters it in the nucleoli (Sherr, 1998; Sharpless and DePinho, 1999; Weber et al., 1999; Zhang and Xiong, 1999; Tao and Levine, 1999; Honda and Yasuda, 1999; Weber et al., 2000). In this manner, upregulation of ARF expression produces the stabilization of p53 which, in turn, results in cell-cycle arrest or apoptosis. The two known critical functions of murine p19^{ARF}, binding to MDM2 and nucleolar localization, are contained in the amino-terminal region encoded by exon 1 β (Weber et al., 1999; Weber et al., 2000; Quelle et al., 1997).

The normal levels of INK4a and ARF expression are extremely low in tissues and primary cells derived from young individuals (Zindy et al., 1997; Zindy et al., 1997; Nielsen et al., 1999; Thullberg et al., 2000). The expression of these genes is significantly upregulated during organismal aging, in vitro replicative senescence, and by the presence of activated oncogenes (Zindy et al., 1997; Zindy et al., 1997; Nielsen et al., 1999; Thullberg et al., 2000; Huschtscha and Reddel, 1999; Serrano et al., 1997; Lin et al., 1998; Palmero et al., 1998; Zindy et al., 1998; de Stanchina et al., 1998; Bates et al., 1998). The activation of the INK4a/ARF locus in response to these mitogenic stresses results in cell-cycle arrest or apoptosis, thus acting as a safeguard mechanism to prevent the emergence of tumor cells (Weinberg, 1997; Sherr, 1998).

Two mutations affecting the INK4a/ARF locus have been introduced so far into the mouse germline: simultaneous elimination of exons 2 and 3 (Δ 2,3) (Serrano et al., 1996); and elimination of exon 1 β (Δ 1 β) without affecting p16^{INK4a} expression (Kamijo et al., 1997). Both mutant mouse strains have a similar tumor susceptibility phenotype, developing sarcomas and lymphomas before one year of age (Serrano et al., 1996; Kamijo et al., 1997; Kamijo et al., 1999). The Δ 2,3 mutation completely abolishes p16^{INK4a} function, among other reasons because the exon 2-encoded domain of p16^{INK4a} is absolutely essential for interaction with CDK4 and CDK6 (Russo et al., 1998; Brotherton et al., 1998). However, this is not necessarily the case for p19^{ARF} since all the known functional domains of p19^{ARF} are encoded by exon 1 β (Weber et al., 1999; Weber et al., 2000; Quelle et al., 1997). Here, we examine the functional status of ARF in Δ 2,3 cells.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Cell culture

Mice of wild-type and INK4a/ARF ^{Δ 2,3} (Serrano et al., 1996) genotypes were maintained in a mixed C57Bl/6;129/Sv genetic background. Primary mouse embryo fibroblasts (MEFs) were prepared from day 13.5 embryos, as previously described (Pantoja and

Serrano, 1999). MEFs were serially passaged according to the 3T3 protocol (Pantoja and Serrano, 1999). Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (Gibco) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Sigma). RNA from tissues was obtained from 2 month old mice.

2.2. Characterization of cDNA and genomic DNA

3'-RACE-PCR was performed using the Marathon kit (Clontech) following the manufacturer's instructions. As starting material, we used total RNA from early passage Δ 2,3 MEFs. After cDNA synthesis and adaptor ligation, we performed nested PCR: 1st PCR using primer MB52 (5'-GAGGGAGTACAGCAGCGGGAG-3') complementary to ARF exon 1 β , and primer AP1 complementary to the adaptor (see Marathon kit); 2nd PCR using primer MB5 (5'-ATGGGTCGCAGGTTCTTG-3') complementary to ARF exon 1 β , and primer AP2 complementary to the adaptor (see Marathon kit).

A genomic BAC containing NTP16 was isolated from the BAC ES Down-to-the-Well library (Genome Systems) (genetic background 129/Sv) using a PCR screening strategy with primers that amplify the 3'-terminal region of NTP16: Abtrans-F (5'-CAAG-GAAACCGATGGAGG-3') and Abtrans-R (5'-CCCACCTTATCCCAATCC-3'). The exon structure of NTP16 was obtained by direct sequencing of the above-mentioned BAC clone using primers based on NTP16 sequences obtained here or previously deposited in the GenBank (accession numbers AF032968 and AF032969). The flanking intronic sequences are available from the authors on request.

2.3. Retroviral transduction

For retroviral gene transfer, we used constructs containing human H-rasV12 oncogene in vector pBabe-puro, or adenoviral oncoprotein E1A (12S) in vector pWZL-hygro (Serrano et al., 1997). Retroviral production and infection were performed essentially as described (Serrano et al., 1997). Early-passage MEFs were infected and 24 h after cells were selected with either 2.5 μ g/ml puromycin or with 75 μ g/ml hygromycin. After selection was complete (3–7 days), cultures were processed for preparation of RNA and protein extracts.

2.4. RNA analysis

Total RNA was extracted using TriZol (Gibco-BRL) following the manufacturer's instructions. For Northern blots, 10 μ g of total RNA were electrophoresed in denaturing agarose gels, transferred to Hybond-N+ membranes, and probed according to standard procedures. The following probes were used: for ARF exon 1 β , we used a PCR fragment of 230 bp produced by primers mE1 β -F (5'-GTCACAGT-GAGGCCGCTG-3') and mE1 β -R (5'-TGGTCCAGGATTCCGGTG-3'); for NTP16 exon 4, a PCR fragment of 330 bp produced by primers Abtrans-F and Abtrans-R (see sequences above). Probes were labeled by random priming with radioactively labeled deoxynucleotides. Hybridizations were performed in high-stringency conditions. After exposure, probes were stripped and membranes were subsequently

hybridized with a probe derived from the γ -actin gene to estimate the amount of RNA loaded in each lane.

The expression pattern of NTp16 in adult mouse tissues was determined by RT-PCR using the following primer pair: NTp16a-F (5'-AGCAGCCTCGCAATGGAA-3') complementary to NTp16 exon 1; and Abtrans-R (see sequence above) complementary to NTp16 exon 4. Similarly, the expression of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript was determined by RT-PCR using the following pair of primers: MB5 complementary to ARF exon 1 β , and Abtrans-R complementary to NTp16 exon 4 (see sequences above). PCR reactions were electrophoresed in agarose gels and subsequently transferred to Hybond-N+ membranes. Visualization of both PCR amplification products (NTp16 and ARF-NTp16) was done by hybridization with a probe derived from NTp16 exon 4 (see above). The integrity of the RNA samples was determined by performing RT-PCR reactions using primers against two different exons of β -actin, β -F (5'-GTGGGCCGCTCTAGGCACCAA-3') and β -R (5'-CTCTTTGATGTCACGCACGATTTC-3').

2.5. Protein analysis

[³⁵S]-methionine-labeled ARF and ARF-NTp16 were synthesized by coupled in vitro transcription and translation using a TNT (Promega) kit, according to the manufacturer's instructions (in a 50 μ l final volume). The templates for the reactions were plasmids containing the cDNAs of ARF and ARF-NTp16. For immunoprecipitation, 5 μ l of the TNT reaction were diluted to a final volume of 200 μ l with ice cold IP buffer (150 mM NaCl, 50 mM Tris pH 8.0, 1% NP40) plus a cocktail of protease inhibitors, and 1 μ g of anti-ARF antibody (R562, AbCam Ltd.). This antibody is raised against a peptide corresponding to positions 54–75 of murine ARF, which includes ten amino acids (positions 54–63) encoded by exon 1 β . The mixtures were incubated overnight at 4°C with rotation. To collect immune complexes, 25 μ l of protein G-Sepharose slurry (GammaBind G, Amersham Pharmacia Biotech), previously blocked with 3% powder milk in PBS, were added to the mixtures, for 1 h, at 4°C. The beads were then washed three times with ice-cold IP buffer, and proteins were released by adding 25 μ l of 2 $\times$ SDS loading buffer, followed by 5 min boiling. Proteins were resolved in a 12% SDS-polyacrylamide gel, and visualized by autoradiography.

For immunoblotting, cells were lysed in IP buffer plus a cocktail of protease inhibitors. After 10 min on ice, cellular debris were removed by centrifugation (14000 rpm, 10 min). Protein concentration was measured using the BioRad DC Protein Assay Kit. Samples corresponding to 40 μ g of protein were resolved on 15% SDS-PAGE gels, wet-transferred to nitrocellulose (BioRad) and immunoblotted. Membranes were incubated with rabbit antibody R562 (see above), 1:200 dilution, followed by a 1:1000 dilution of HRP-linked anti-rabbit as secondary antibody. Membranes were subsequently probed with monoclonal antibody AC-15 against β -actin (1:10000) (Sigma), and HRP-linked anti-mouse (DAKO) as secondary antibody. Detection was performed by chemiluminescence using ECL (Amersham).

Fig. 1. Identification of a chimeric transcript between exon 1 β of ARF and exon 4 of NTP16. (A) Northern blot of total RNA prepared from wild-type or $\Delta 2,3$ primary MEFs, as indicated, hybridized with a probe from exon 1 β of ARF (left panel) or with a probe from exon 4 of NTP16 (right panel). The figure shows one experiment representative of six independent experiments (see also Figs. 3 and 4), (B) Sequence of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript. The box comprises exon 1 β of ARF; the remaining sequence corresponds to exon 4 of NTP16. The amino acid sequence of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 peptide is indicated. (C) Sequence of NTP16 cDNA and the translated amino acid sequence of its first open reading frame. Exon boundaries are indicated with arrowheads, (D) Scheme of the INK4a/ARF and NTP16 loci in wild-type (upper) and $\Delta 2,3$ (lower) mouse strains. Sizes and distances are not to scale. Exons are indicated with black boxes, except for the neo-resistance marker (white box). Promoters are indicated with flags, and splicing events are indicated with thin lines.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of an exon 1 β -containing transcript in homozygous *INK4a/ARF* $\Delta 2,3$ cells

We initially obtained evidence for the existence of an exon 1 β -containing transcript in

homozygous INK4a/ARF^{Δ2,3} cells (abbreviated as Δ2,3) by analyzing total RNA from early-passage mouse embryo fibroblasts (MEFs). Unexpectedly, Δ2,3 cells presented a transcript that hybridized with exon 1β (Fig. 1(A); left panel). The abundance of this transcript was quantified with a phosphorimager using Northern blots derived from six independent cultures of wild-type and Δ2,3 primary MEFs. The levels of the exon 1β-containing transcript in Δ2,3 cells was $32 \pm 13\%$ compared to ARF transcript levels in wild-type MEFs (100%). To characterize the identity of the exon 1β-containing transcript in Δ2,3 MEFs, we performed 3'-RACE-PCR using forward primers complementary to exon 1β (see Experimental procedures). The most abundant product obtained had a size consistent with a transcript formed by exon 1β followed by an extension of ~800 nt (not shown). Sequencing of this 3'-RACE-PCR product revealed that the transcript in Δ2,3 cells is formed by exon 1β followed by the 3'-terminal region of a gene already deposited in GenBank (accession number AF032968 and AF032969) (Fig. 1(B)). This gene was originally isolated as a putative regulator of the immunological response to LPS (Jin et al., 1997), however its involvement in this process has not been established and its function is presently unknown. We have named this gene NTP16, for Next-To-p16 (see below), and we will refer to the transcript in Δ2,3 cells as the chimeric ARF-NTP16 transcript.

3.2. Genomic structure of NTP16

To locate the genomic position of NTP16 in relation to the INK4a/ARF locus, we isolated a mouse genomic clone containing NTP16 from a bacterial artificial chromosome (BAC) library (see Experimental procedures). PCR analysis indicated that this genomic clone contains not only NTP16, but also exons 1α, 2 and 3 from the INK4a/ARF locus (not shown), thus confirming that the two loci, NTP16 and INK4a/ARF, are indeed genetically linked. Similar PCR analysis using smaller genomic fragments indicated that NTP16 is more than 7 kb downstream of INK4a/ARF exon 3 (not shown).

To better understand the origin of the chimeric ARF-NTP16 transcript, we determined the exon-intron boundaries of NTP16. For this, we sequenced the above-mentioned BAC using primers complementary to NTP16 cDNA, finding that the NTP16 gene is formed by four exons (Fig. 1(C)). From these data, it became immediately clear that the sequence fused to ARF exon 1β in Δ2,3 cells corresponds to the last exon (exon 4) of NTP16 (Fig. 1(B)).

As it was mentioned before, there are two NTP16-related sequences in the GenBank, whose composition can be now interpreted as follows: sequence AF032969 is composed by NTP16 exons 1-2-4; and sequence AF032968 is composed by an alternative exon 1 followed by NTP16 exons 2-3-4. We have been unable to obtain any RT-PCR product using primers against the alternative exon 1 present in AF032968, and for this reason we have not considered its existence in the scheme shown in Fig. 1(D) nor in subsequent analysis. The full-length NTP16 transcript contains one open reading frame, whose start codon is the first one in the transcript, and that encodes a peptide of 8.8 kDa (Fig. 1(C)). We detected no significant similarities between this peptide and the current databases. It should be noted that the open reading frame that encodes the 8.8 kDa peptide does not include NTP16 exon 4 (compare Fig. 1(B) and (C)).

Fig. 2. Expression of the ARF-NTp16 chimeric transcript in wild-type and $\Delta 2,3$ mouse tissues. Top panels. RT-PCR products specific for the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript (see Experimental procedures) obtained from tissues or primary MEFs, and derived from $\Delta 2,3$ or wild-type mice, as indicated. Reactions were electrophoresed and hybridized to a probe derived from NTP16 exon 4 (see Experimental procedures). The size of the band obtained matched the expected size of 560 bp. Bottom panels. The same RNA samples as above were used to detect β -actin transcripts.

3.3. Expression of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript

We have first considered the possibility that the ARF-NTp16 chimeric transcript could be expressed, not only in $\Delta 2,3$ cells, but also in wild-type cells. To address this, we hybridized total RNA from early-passage MEFs with a probe corresponding to NTP16 exon 4 (Fig. 1(A), right panel). As anticipated, $\Delta 2,3$ MEFs express a transcript that hybridizes with exon 4 of NTP16. In contrast, wild-type MEFs do not express NTP16-derived transcripts at levels detectable by Northern blot (Fig. 1(A)). To characterize in further detail the expression of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript, we performed RT-PCR analysis using primers complementary to ARF exon 1 β (forward primer) and to NTP16 exon 4 (reverse primer). As shown in Fig. 2, ARF-NTp16 is detectable only in $\Delta 2,3$ MEFs, but not in wild-type MEFs. Similarly, the chimeric transcript was readily detected as a PCR product of the predicted size in a number of tissues from $\Delta 2,3$ mice (Fig. 2). Taking into consideration that the chimeric transcript is under the control of the ARF promoter, the above result is in agreement with previous reports showing ubiquitous expression of ARF, although at low levels only detectable by RT-PCR (Zindy et al., 1997; Quelle et al., 1995). No expression of ARF-NTp16 was detected in some $\Delta 2,3$ tissues, including liver and kidney, which had been previously found to express the lowest levels of ARF (Quelle et al., 1995). In contrast to $\Delta 2,3$ tissues, wild-type tissues did not express detectable levels of ARF-NTp16 with the only exception of lung (Fig. 2) and spleen (not shown), both of which showed barely detectable expression of ARF-NTp16. These results indicate that the ARF-NTp16 chimeric transcript is expressed at significant levels only in $\Delta 2,3$ tissues, but not in wild-type tissues.

Fig. 3. Upregulation of the ARF-NTp16 chimeric transcript by accumulation of cell doublings. Northern blot of total RNA prepared from wild-type or $\Delta 2,3$ primary MEFs with a low (lo; PDL <2) or high (hi; PDL = 8–10) number of accumulated doublings, as indicated, hybridized with a probe from ARF exon 1 β . Cultures were passaged according to the 3T3 protocol. Data correspond to three independent wild-type MEF preparations (derived from embryos D71, D55 and D52) and to three independent $\Delta 2,3$ MEF preparations (from embryos C11, C18 and C5). All membranes had similar RNA loading as judged from the signal obtained with a γ -actin probe, shown only in the case of cultures D52 and C5 for simplicity.

3.4. Regulation of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript in $\Delta 2,3$ MEFs

We reasoned that if the expression of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript is regulated by the ARF promoter, then it must be subject to the same regulatory mechanisms that control ARF expression in wild-type cells. ARF levels are upregulated upon the accumulation of cell doublings or *population doublings level* (PDL) in MEFs (Zindy et al., 1998). We compared by Northern analysis the levels of ARF and ARF-NTp16 transcripts in cultures with low (PDL = 2) or high (PDL = 8–10) accumulated doublings (Fig. 3). Interestingly, the ARF-NTp16 transcript was found to be upregulated in $\Delta 2,3$ cells to a similar relative extent as the ARF transcript in wild-type cells (Fig. 3).

It is well established that ARF mRNA levels are upregulated in response to various oncogenic stresses, such as Ras, E1a and Myc (Palmero et al., 1998; Zindy et al., 1998; de Stanchina et al., 1998). In particular, we analyzed ARF-NTp16 transcript levels in primary $\Delta 2,3$ MEFs retrovirally transduced with oncogenic Ras or with the viral oncoprotein E1a (Fig. 4). We observed that the ARF-NTp16 transcript is upregulated in the presence of these oncogenic stresses in a similar relative manner as the ARF transcript in wild-type cells (Fig. 4). We conclude that the levels of ARF-NTp16 transcript in $\Delta 2,3$ cells are subject to similar regulatory controls as the normal ARF transcript in wild-type cells.

Fig. 4. Upregulation of the ARF-NTp16 chimeric transcript by oncogenic Ras and by E1a. Northern blot of total RNA prepared from wild-type or $\Delta 2,3$ primary MEFs retrovirally transduced with oncogenic Ras (R), E1a 12S (E), or the corresponding empty vectors (V), as indicated, hybridized with a probe from ARF exon 1 β . The lower part corresponds to the same membrane after hybridization with a probe against γ -actin. Two independent experiments were performed with similar results.

3.5. Lack of detectable levels of chimeric ARF-NTp16 peptide

The chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript has capacity to produce a peptide formed by the ARF domain encoded by exon 1 β followed by a peptide derived from the non-coding 3'-terminal exon of NTp16, and which has a predicted molecular weight of 16.7 kDa (Fig. 1(B)). This peptide can be produced by *in vitro* translation using rabbit reticulocyte extracts (Fig. 5(A)). The chimeric ARF-NTp16 peptide was specifically immunoprecipitated using a commercial antibody against murine ARF (see Experimental procedures) (Fig. 5(A)). Based on these results, we tested by immunoblot the same cells used for the experiment shown in Fig. 4, and that had been infected with empty retroviruses or with retroviruses encoding oncogenic Ras or E1A. As it can be seen in Fig. 5(B), no evidence could be obtained for the presence of the ARF-NTp16 peptide in $\Delta 2,3$ cells, whereas we could clearly detect ARF in wild-type cells (Fig. 5(B)). Also, we have been unable to detect the chimeric ARF-NTp16 peptide after transfection of expression constructs containing the ARF-NTp16 cDNA under the control of strong promoters, such as CMV or LTR (results not shown). It is conceivable that the ARF-NTp16 peptide is poorly expressed either because of a short-half life due to inadequate folding, or because sub-optimal codon usage. These results suggest that $\Delta 2,3$ cells do not retain ARF functionality, at least to a significant extent.

3.6. Expression of NTp16 in $\Delta 2,3$ mice

We have shown above that, in $\Delta 2,3$ cells, transcription initiated at the ARF promoter results in the production of a chimeric transcript between the ARF and NTp16 genes. This opens the possibility that the $\Delta 2,3$ mutation could be affecting the expression of the normal, full-length, NTp16 transcript. To address this issue, we have analyzed by RT-PCR the expression of NTp16 in tissues of wild-type and $\Delta 2,3$ mice (Fig. 6). For this, we used PCR primers against NTp16 exon 1 and NTp16 exon 4. Expression of NTp16 was consistently found in the thymus of wild-type mice, but not in other tissues. Interestingly, in $\Delta 2,3$ mice, expression of NTp16 was found at significant levels, not only in thymus, but

Fig. 5. Lack of detectable ARF-NTp16 chimeric peptide *in vivo*. A. The products of *in vitro*-translated and [³⁵S]-labeled ARF and ARF-NTp16 were electrophoresed directly (input), after immunoprecipitation with a commercial antibody against murine ARF (see Experimental procedures), or after a mock immunoprecipitation with empty G-Sepharose beads. B. Immunoblot of protein extracts from the same experiment shown in Fig. 4 with a commercial antibody against murine ARF (see Experimental procedures). Primary MEFs of the indicated genotype were retrovirally transduced with an empty vector (V), oncogenic Ras (R), or the oncoprotein E1a (E). No evidence for the presence of an ARF-NTp16 chimeric peptide could be obtained in Δ2,3 cells. The immunoblot was re-probed with anti-β actin to demonstrate equal protein loading.

also in tissues such as brain, lung, and large intestine that do not normally express NTp16 (Fig. 6). In addition to the most abundant RT-PCR product, which matched the expected size, some bands of higher sizes were also detected although at lower levels (Fig. 6). The nature of these amplification products has not been determined. These results indicate that the Δ2,3 mutation is affecting the normal expression pattern of the NTp16 gene.

4. Discussion

Here, we have analyzed the functional status of ARF in the absence of the natural exons 2 and 3. We found that the ARF promoter remains active in the absence of the genomic region spanning from exons 2–3, and generates a chimeric transcript between ARF and the gene immediately downstream of the INK4a/ARF locus, which we have called NTp16 (Next-To-p16). The levels of the chimeric ARF-NTp16 transcript are approximately 30% relative to those of the normal ARF transcript in wild-type cells (100%). Furthermore, the chimeric transcript is upregulated in response to the same stimuli that upregulate the normal ARF transcript, such as the accumulation of cell doublings and the presence of

Fig. 6. Expression of NTP16 in wild-type and $\Delta 2,3$ mouse tissues. Top panels. RT-PCR products specific for the NTP16 transcript (see Experimental procedures) obtained from tissues or primary MEFs, and derived from $\Delta 2,3$ or wild-type mice, as indicated. Reactions were electrophoresed and hybridized to a probe derived from NTP16 exon 4 (see Experimental procedures). The size of the most abundant band matched the expected size of 764 bp. Bottom panels. The same RNA samples as above were used to detect β -actin transcripts

oncogenic stresses. Thus, a first conclusion from this data is that the genomic region comprising [exon 2-intron-exon 3] does not contain important regulatory sequences for ARF expression.

The generation of the ARF-NTP16 chimeric transcript in $\Delta 2,3$ cells implies that transcription originating from the ARF promoter reaches the NTP16 gene, which provides adequate splicing and polyadenylation signals. The polyadenylation signal present in the neo-resistance marker (Fig. 1(D)) is ignored probably due to the absence of appropriate splicing signals between exon 1 β and the neo-marker, which would be consistent with the accepted view that polyadenylation is coupled with splicing (Minvielle-Sebastia and Keller, 1999). Curiously, the ARF-NTP16 chimeric transcript involves the 3'-terminal exon of NTP16 (exon 4), but not the upstream NTP16 exons 2 and 3. It is possible that these latter exons are subject to splicing regulation. In this regard, we have obtained evidence indicating the existence of alternatively spliced NTP16 transcripts (unpublished observations).

The ARF-NTP16 transcript has the capacity to produce a chimeric peptide containing the exon 1 β -encoded domain of ARF. However, we have been unable to obtain evidence for the accumulation of the chimeric peptide in $\Delta 2,3$ cells. Moreover, we have not detected the presence of the chimeric peptide after transfection of expression constructs containing the ARF-NTP16 cDNA under strong promoters. It is conceivable that the chimeric peptide is unstable or is not properly folded, having a very short half-life. Additionally, the chimeric ARF-NTP16 transcript could be sub-optimally translated due to the fact that the exon 4 of NTP16 is not a coding exon in wild-type cells. We conclude that $\Delta 2,3$ cells

do not possess ARF functionality despite retaining significant levels of an exon 1 β -containing transcript.

Finally, we have explored the possibility that the Δ 2,3 mutation could affect the normal expression pattern of NTp16. The expression of NTp16 in wild-type mice is mostly restricted to the thymus, an observation that is in agreement with the putative role of NTp16 in mediating immunological responses to LPS (Jin et al., 1997). Interestingly, the Δ 2,3 mutation produces a significant deregulation of the NTp16 gene, becoming expressed in tissues where NTp16 is not normally expressed. The functional consequences of this abnormal expression of NTp16 in Δ 2,3 mice should await the elucidation of the normal function of NTp16.

This study also provides information relevant to the characterization of the region surrounding the INK4a/ARF locus. This is particularly important because there is evidence pointing to the existence of one or more tumor suppressor genes in the immediate vicinity of the INK4a/ARF locus (Ohta et al., 1996; Lydiatt et al., 1998; Mariatos et al., 2000; Schmid et al., 1998). Recently, the characterization of a deletion in a human tumor has allowed to identify the gene immediately upstream of the INK4b and INK4a/ARF loci (Schmid et al., 2000). Here, we report the identification of the gene immediately downstream of the INK4a/ARF locus. Previously, the closest gene downstream of the INK4a/ARF locus was the methylthioadenosine phosphorylase (MTAP) gene (Nobori et al., 1996). A high-resolution mapping of deletions in human non-small cell lung carcinomas concluded that the genomic region, of approximately 100 kb, that extends between the INK4a/ARF locus and the MTAP gene is more commonly deleted than the INK4a/ARF locus itself (Schmid et al., 1998). Based on our findings, the NTp16 gene is located between the INK4a/ARF and MTAP loci, and for this reason its putative role as a tumor suppressor should be explored. We detected no significant amino acid homology between NTp16 and the current protein or DNA databases. Studies are presently under way to determine whether NTp16 has properties consistent with a tumor suppressor gene.

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References

- Bates, S., Phillips, A.C., Clark, P.A., Stott, F., Peters, G., Ludwig, R.L., Vousden, K.H., 1998. p14^{ARF} links the tumor suppressors Rb and p53. *Nature* 395, 124–125.
- Brotherton, D.H., Dhanaraj, V., Wick, S., Brizuela, L., Domaille, P.J., Volyanik, E., Xu, X., Parsini, E., Smith, B.O., Archer, S.J., Serrano, M., Brenner, S.L., Blundell, T.L., Laue, E.D., 1998. Crystal structure of the complex of the cyclin D-dependent kinase Cdk6 bound to the cell-cycle inhibitor p19^{INK4d}. *Nature* 395, 244–250.

- Honda, R., Yasuda, H., 1999. Association of p19^{ARF} with Mdm2 inhibits ubiquitin ligase activity of Mdm2 for tumour suppressor p53. *EMBO J.* 18, 22–27.
- Huschtscha, L.I., Reddel, R.R., 1999. p16^{INK4a} and the control of cellular proliferative life span. *Carcinogenesis* 20, 921–926.
- Jin, F., Nathan, C., Radzioch, D., Ding, A., 1997. Secretory leukocyte protease inhibitor: A macrophage product induced by and antagonistic to bacterial lipopolysaccharide. *Cell* 88, 417–426.
- Kamijo, T., Zindy, F., Roussel, M.F., Quelle, D.E., Downing, J.R., Ashmun, R.A., Grosveld, G., Sherr, C.J., 1997. Tumor suppression at the mouse INK4a locus mediated by the alternative reading frame product p19^{ARF}. *Cell* 91, 649–659.
- Kamijo, T., Bodner, S., van de Kamp, E., Randle, D.H., Sherr, C.J., 1999. Tumor spectrum in *ARF*-deficient mice. *Cancer Res.* 59, 2217–2222.
- Lin, A.W., Barradas, M., Stone, J.C., van Aelst, L., Serrano, M., Lowe, S.W., 1998. Premature senescence involving p53 and p16 is activated in response to constitutive MEK/MAPK mitogenic signaling. *Genes Dev.* 12, 3008–3019.
- Lydiatt, W.M., Davidson, B.J., Schantz, S.P., Caruana, S., Chaganti, R.S., 1998. 9p21 deletion correlates with recurrence in head and neck cancer. *Head Neck* 20, 113–118.
- Mariatos, G., Gorgoulis, V.G., Zacharatos, P., Kotsinas, A., Vogiatzi, T., Rassidakis, G., Foukas, P., Liloglou, T., Tiniakos, D., Angelou, N., Manolis, E.N., Veslemes, M., Field, J.K., Kittas, C., 2000. Expression of p16(INK4A) and alterations of the 9p21-23 chromosome region in non-small-cell lung carcinomas: relationship with tumor growth parameters and ploidy status. *Int. J. Cancer* 89, 133–141.
- Minvielle-Sebastia, L., Keller, W., 1999. mRNA polyadenylation and its coupling to other RNA processing reactions and to transcription. *Curr. Opin. Cell Biol.* 11, 352–357.
- Nielsen, G.P., Stemmer-Rachamimov, A.O., Shaw, J., Roy, J.E., Koh, J., Louis, D.N., 1999. Immunohistochemical survey of p16^{INK4A} expression in normal human adult and infant tissues. *Lab. Invest.* 79, 1137–1143.
- Nobori, T., Takabayashi, K., Tran, P., Orvis, L., Batova, A., Yu, A.L., Carson, D.A., 1996. Genomic cloning of methylthioadenosine phosphorylase: A purine metabolic enzyme deficient in multiple different cancers. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 93, 6203–6208.
- Ohta, M., Berd, D., Shimizu, M., Nagai, H., Cotticelli, M.-G., Mastrangelo, M., Shields, J.A., Shields, C.L., Croce, C.M., Huebner, K., 1996. Deletion mapping of chromosome region 9p21-p22 surrounding the CDKN2 locus in melanoma. *Int. J. Cancer* 65, 762–767.
- Palmero, I., Pantoja, C., Serrano, M., 1998. p19^{ARF} links the tumour suppressor p53 to Ras. *Nature* 395, 125–126.
- Pantoja, C., Serrano, M., 1999. Murine fibroblasts lacking p21 undergo senescence and are resistant to transformation by oncogenic Ras. *Oncogene* 18, 4974–4982.
- Quelle, D.E., Zindy, F., Ashmun, R.A., Sherr, C.J., 1995. Alternative reading frames of the *INK4a* tumor suppressor gene encode two unrelated proteins capable of inducing cell cycle arrest. *Cell* 83, 993–1000.
- Quelle, D.E., Cheng, M., Ashmun, R.A., Sherr, C.J., 1997. Cancer-associated mutations at the *INK4a* locus cancel cell cycle arrest by p16^{INK4a} but not by the alternative reading frame protein p19^{ARF}. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 94, 3436–3440.
- Ruas, M., Peters, G., 1998. The p16^{INK4a/CDKN2A} tumor suppressor and its relatives. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1378, F115–F177.
- Russo, A.A., Tong, L., Lee, J.-O., Jeffrey, P.D., Pavletich, N.P., 1998. Structural basis for the inhibition of the cyclin-dependent kinase Cdk6 by the tumour suppressor p16^{INK4a}. *Nature* 395, 237–243.
- de Stanchina, E., McCurrach, M., Zindy, F., Shieh, S.-Y., Ferbeyre, G., Samuelson, A.V., Prives, C., Roussel, M.F., Sherr, C.J., Lowe, S.W., 1998. E1A signaling to p53 involves the p19^{ARF} tumor suppressor. *Genes Dev.* 12, 2434–2442.
- Schmid, M., Malicki, D., Nobori, T., Rosenbach, M.D., Campbell, K., Carson, D.A., Carrera, C.J., 1998. Homozygous deletions of methylthioadenosine phosphorylase (*MTAP*) are more frequent than p16^{INK4A} (*CDKN2*) homozygous deletions in primary non-small cell lung cancers (NSCLC). *Oncogene* 17, 2669–2675.
- Schmid, M., Sen, M., Rosenbach, M.D., Carrera, C.J., Friedman, H., Carson, D.A., 2000. A methylthioadenosine phosphorylase (*MTAP*) fusion transcript identifies a new gene on chromosome 9p21 that is frequently deleted in cancer. *Oncogene* 19, 5747–5754.
- Serrano, M., Lee, H.-W., Chin, L., Cordon-Cardo, C., Beach, D., DePinho, R.A., 1996. Role of the INK4a locus in tumor suppression and cell mortality. *Cell* 85, 27–37.

- Serrano, M., Lin, A.W., McCurrach, M.E., Beach, D., Lowe, S.W., 1997. Oncogenic ras provokes premature cell senescence associated with the accumulation of p53 and p16^{INK4a}. *Cell* 88, 593–602.
- Serrano, M., 1997. The tumor suppressor protein p16^{INK4a}. *Exp. Cell Res.* 237, 7–13.
- Sharpless, N.E., DePinho, R.A., 1999. The *INK4A/ARF* locus and its two gene products. *Curr. Opin. Genet. Dev.* 9, 22–30.
- Sherr, C.J., 1998. Tumor surveillance via the ARF-p53 pathway. *Genes Dev.* 12, 2984–2991.
- Tao, W., Levine, A.J., 1999. P19^{ARF} stabilizes p53 by blocking nucleo-cytoplasmic shuttling of Mdm2. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 96, 6937–6941.
- Thullberg, M., Bartkova, J., Khan, S., Hansen, K., Rönnestrand, L., Lukas, J., Strauss, M., Bartek, J., 2000. Distinct versus redundant properties among members of the INK4 family of cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors. *FEBS Lett.* 470, 161–166.
- Weber, J.D., Taylor, L.J., Roussel, M.F., Sherr, C.J., Bar-Sagi, D., 1999. Nucleolar Arf sequesters Mdm2 and activates p53. *Nat. Cell Biol.* 1, 20–26.
- Weber, J.D., Kuo, M.-L., Bothner, B., DiGiandomino, E.L., Kriwacki, R.W., Roussel, M.F., Sherr, C.J., 2000. Cooperative signals governing ARF-Mdm2 interaction and nucleolar localization of the complex. *Mol. Cell Biol.* 20, 2517–2528.
- Weinberg, R.A., 1997. The cat and mouse games that genes, viruses, and cells play. *Cell* 88, 573–575.
- Zhang, Y., Xiong, Y., 1999. Mutations in human ARF exon 2 disrupt its nucleolar localization and impair its ability to block nuclear export of MDM2 and p53. *Mol. Cell* 3, 579–591.
- Zindy, F., Quelle, D.E., Roussel, M.F., Sherr, C.J., 1997. Expression of the p16^{INK4a} tumor suppressor versus other INK4 family members during mouse development and aging. *Oncogene* 15, 203–211.
- Zindy, F., Soares, H., Herzog, K.H., Morgan, J., Sherr, C.J., Roussel, M.F., 1997. Expression of INK4 inhibitors of cyclin D-dependent kinases during mouse brain development. *Cell Growth Differ.* 8, 1139–1150.
- Zindy, F., Eischen, C.M., Randle, D.H., Kamijo, T., Cleveland, J.L., Sherr, C.J., Roussel, M.F., 1998. Myc signaling via the ARF tumor suppressor regulates p53-dependent apoptosis and immortalization. *Genes Dev.* 12, 2424–2433.